

EFFICACY OF *LODHRA-KATUTUMBI TAILA YONIPICHUDHARANA* IN *YONIBHRAMSHA* (PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Pelvic organ prolapse (*Yonibhramsha*) is a common gynecological condition that significantly affects the quality of life of women, often presenting with symptoms such as feeling of mass in vagina, urinary disturbances, and low back pain. Ayurvedic interventions, particularly local therapies, have proven to be much more beneficial as alternatives to surgical management. **Case summary:** A 42-year-old married female presented to the Prasuti Tantra and Stree Roga OPD of Alva's Ayurveda Medical College & Hospital with complaints of mass per vagina for two months, increased frequency of micturition, and low back pain for 10 days. She had a history of four full-term normal vaginal deliveries, with her last childbirth 12 years ago. Clinical examination revealed anterior vaginal wall bulge, cervix descent below ischial spines, and retroverted uterus. POP-Q assessment confirmed Pelvic Organ Prolapse.

Intervention: The patient was treated with *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* for 14 days each, over two

consecutive months and follow up was done on 21st day following treatment. Lifestyle modifications including Kegel's exercises, fiber-rich diet, adequate hydration, and avoidance of strenuous activities were advised. **Results:** Objective improvement was noted in POP-Q

parameters, with progressive reduction in Aa, Ba, and C points. Subjective symptoms improved significantly: the feeling of mass per vagina resolved by the 14th day of the first month, low back pain reduced from VAS 4/10 to 1/10, and frequency of micturition decreased to 5–6 times/day by follow-up. No adverse effects were reported. **Conclusion:** This case demonstrates that *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana*, along with lifestyle modifications, can be an effective conservative management option for Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP). The therapy provided symptomatic relief and measurable anatomical improvement, highlighting its potential role in non-surgical management of *Yonibhramsha*.

KEYWORDS: *Yonibhramsha*; *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila*; Pelvic Organ Prolapse; *Yonipichudharana*.

INTRODUCTION

Yonibhramsha is a clinical condition in which displacement of female genital organs (uterus and vaginal walls) occur from its normal position. The condition of *Yonibhramsha* is having close resemblance with Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) based on its signs and symptoms like feeling of mass in vagina, low back ache, dyspareunia, urinary and bowel symptoms and white or blood-stained discharge per vagina. POP is one of the common clinical conditions met in day-to-day gynecological practice especially among the parous women.

Integrity of support structures of pelvic organs is fundamental to pelvic organ stability. The Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) occurs due to weakness of the structures supporting the organs in position,^[1] involving supports of vagina like endopelvic fascia, which also forms posterior urethral ligament giving support to urethra, pubocervical fascia, uterosacral ligaments, levator ani muscles with its fascial coverings, levator plate, perineal body and supports of uterus like endopelvic fascia covering the uterus, pericervical ring- connected with pubocervical ligaments, vesicovaginal septum, cardinal ligaments, uterosacral ligaments and rectovaginal septum; pelvic cellular tissue, pelvic floor muscles, levator plate, perineal body and urogenital diaphragm.

It is difficult to assess the true prevalence of POP, as many women do not seek medical attention for their symptoms. However, symptomatic POP has a prevalence of 3% to 6%, and anatomic prolapse occurs in up to 50% of women.^[2] The prevalence of prolapse of the vaginal cuff following hysterectomy was reported to be as high as 6%-12%.^[3] From POP reconstructive surgeries it appears that a woman's lifetime risk of undergoing a surgery for

POP or Stress Urinary Incontinence (SUI) is 11%-20%.^[3] The incidence of POP is highly associated with increased age. It is projected to increase by 46%, by 2050.^[4]

The complications of POP include renal damage, urinary tract infection, upper renal tract infection, in rare cases-vaginal carcinoma is reported over decubitus ulcer and if the ring pessary is left in over a long period.^[4]

Most commonly used conservative treatment in modern science is Pessary treatment, which has complications like vaginal discharge, irritation, ulceration, bleeding, pain and odour, vaginal wall ulceration, fistula formation or bowel herniation, less frequent pessary change has high occurrence of bacterial vaginosis.

With the advancement of age in women, the existing condition may further progress, with increased laxity of pelvic floor, leading to need for surgical management. The complications of surgical management of POP includes haemorrhage, trauma, urinary complications like retention of urine and cystitis, dyspareunia, recurrence of prolapse, vesicovaginal fistula following bladder injury, rectovaginal fistula following rectal injury, vault cellulitis, pelvic abscess, thrombophlebitis, pulmonary embolism, vault prolapse, cervical stenosis.^[5] In some cases, if contraindication for surgery arises, those conditions needs to be managed with conservative methods, which may affect quality of life.

Yonipichudharana is one among the *Sthanika Chikitsa* mentioned for *Yonirogas* in which medicines are administered intravaginally, which can overcome the limitations of conservative and surgical management. As vaginal wall and adjacent tissues are highly vascular and facilitates absorption of drugs through vaginal mucosa and surrounding tissues, the drugs administered through vaginal route, gets absorbed and improves tone, enhances elasticity and firmness of supporting structures and certain drugs may boost collagen production and thus *Yonipichudharana* can prove to be the effective management of POP.

The reference of *Lodhra-Katutumbi* can be found in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*, *Strirogadhikara*, 141th verse and “*Yonidardhyakara*” effect has been mentioned. Here, *Lodhra-Katutumbi* is used in the form of *Taila Kalpana*, as the condition of *Yonibhramsha* being *Vata Dosha* predominant and *Tila Taila* being *Balya*, *Vatashamaka*, *Brimhana*, *Sthairyakara*, *Yonishoolahara* and *Garbhashayashodhana*.

CASE REPORT

A 42 years old married female came to PTSR OPD of Alva's Ayurveda Medical College & Hospital on 22nd September 2024 with the complaints of feeling of mass per vagina since 2 months and associated complaints of increased frequency of micturition and low back pain since 10 days. She is having history of four full-term normal vaginal deliveries, with her last childbirth 12 years ago.

PAST MEDICAL/SURGICAL HISTORY

No H/O Chronic constipation, Chronic cough, Bronchitis, Asthma, Obesity, Neuromuscular Disorders or Connective tissue disorders.

FAMILY HISTORY

No relevant family history.

PERSONAL HISTORY

Diet: Mixed

Food habit: Regular

Appetite: Normal

Digestive power: Good

Bowel habits: Regular, Formed

Micturition: Increased frequency (10-12 times/day)

Addiction: None

Sleep: Disturbed

Nature of work: Housewife

Exercise: None

MENSTRUAL HISTORY

Menarche: At the age of 12 years

LMP: 18/09/2024

Cycle duration: 3-4 days

Cycle length: 28-32 days

Cycle regularity: Regular

Amount of bleeding: 3-4 pads/day

Clots: Absent

Dysmenorrhea: Absent

OBSTETRIC HISTORY

P4L4

Nature of delivery: all FTNVD (Institutional)

LCB: 12 years

Not sterilized

GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

General condition: Good

Height: 5.1 feet

Weight: 52.3 kg

BMI: 21.6 kg/m²

BP: 120/80 mmHg

PR: 72/min

RR: 16/min

Temperature: Afebrile

Pallor: Absent

Cyanosis: Absent

Icterus: Absent

Clubbing: Absent

Lymphadenopathy: Absent

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

- CVS: S1, S2 heard and no murmurs
- RS: Normal vesicular breath sounds heard, no added sounds
- CNS: Conscious and well oriented to place, person and time
- P/A: Soft, non-tender

LOCAL EXAMINATION

External genitalia: Mild widening of vaginal introitus

Per speculum: Cervix healthy

Vagina – rugae flattened

Anterior vaginal wall bulge +

Posterior vaginal wall - normal

Per vaginal: Uterus retroverted, normal in size

Cervix descended below ischial spines, midline

Fornices free

ASHTASTHANA PARIKSHA

Nadi: Vata Pittaja Shabda: Prakrita
Mala: Prakrita Sparsha: Sheeta
Mootra: Vaikrita Drik: Prakrita
Jihwa: Alipta Akriti: Madhyama

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana for 14 days for 2 consecutive months.

LIFESTYLE AND DIETARY ADVICE

- Kegel's exercise
- Plenty of fiber rich diet like whole grains, spinach, sweet potato, beans, carrot, berries, banana, nuts, seeds and lentils
- Good hydration
- Avoid heavy weight lifting strenuous activities, prolonged standing and squatting for long hours for cooking, cleaning and other works.

ASSESSMENT

Assessment was done by documenting changes in the 9 points of POP Q Scale and improvement in the subjective symptoms on 1st, 7th and 14th day of 2 consecutive months and follow up on 21st day following treatment.

Table no. 1: Description of 9 points in POP Q Scale.

Site	Description	Range
Aa	Anterior vaginal wall, midline 3cm proximal to external urinary meatus (point of urethrovesical crease)	-3cm to +3cm
Ba	Anterior vaginal wall, most distal position between Aa and anterior fornix	-3cm to +TVL
C	Cervix or vaginal cuff	-
D	Posterior fornix or vaginal apex	-
Ap	Posterior vaginal wall, midline 3cm proximal to hymen	-3cm to +3cm
Bp	Posterior vaginal wall, most distal position, between Ap and posterior fornix	-3cm to +TVL
Gh	External urinary meatus to posterior midline hymenal ring	-
TVL	Depth of vagina when point D or C is reduced to normal position	-
Pb	Posterior hymen to anal opening	-

(TVL- Total Vaginal Length, Pb- Perineal body, Gh- Genital hiatus)

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULT**Table no. 2: Changes in 9 points of POP Q scale.**

	1 st month			2 nd month			Follow up
	1 st day 23/09/24	7 th day 29/09/24	14 th day 06/10/24	1 st day 19/10/24	7 th day 25/10/24	14 th day 01/11/24	21 st day 08/11/24
Aa	-2.0 cm	-2.2	-2.5 cm	-2.4 cm	-2.6 cm	-2.8 cm	-2.7 cm
Ba	-2.1 cm	-2.2 cm	-2.4 cm	-2.4 cm	-2.5 cm	-2.7 cm	-2.6 cm
C	-3.8 cm	-4.5 cm	-5.5 cm	-5.3 cm	-5.6 cm	-6 cm	-6 cm
GH	5.5 cm	5.5 cm	5.4 cm	5.4 cm	5.3 cm	5.3 cm	5.3 cm
PB	2.9 cm	2.9 cm	3 cm	3 cm	3.1 cm	3.1 cm	3.1 cm
TVL	8.5 cm	8.5 cm	8.5 cm	8.5 cm	8.5 cm	8.5 cm	8.5 cm
Ap	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm
Bp	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm	-3 cm
D	-8.5 cm	-8.5 cm	-8.5 cm	-8.5 cm	-8.5 cm	-8.5 cm	-8.5 cm

Table no. 3: Observation on subjective symptoms.

	1 st month			2 nd month			Follow up
	1 st day 23/09/24	7 th day 29/09/24	14 th day 06/10/24	1 st day 19/10/24	7 th day 25/10/24	14 th day 01/11/24	21 st day 08/11/24
Feeling of mass per vagina	Present	Present	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
Low back ache	VAS 4/10	VAS 3/10	VAS 3/10	VAS 3/10	VAS 2/10	VAS 1/10	VAS 1/10
Frequency of micturition	10-12 t/day	8-10 t/day	6-8 t/day	6-8 t/day	6-7 t/day	5-6 t/day	5-6 t/day

DISCUSSION

Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) is a significant health problem affecting women worldwide, especially in developing countries where multiparity, poor nutrition, and early resumption of physical activities in puerperium are prevalent. POP is having high anatomical prevalence, impact on women's physical, psychological, and sexual wellbeing, and socio-cultural implications, which often lead to under-reporting and delayed treatment.^[6] Modern management primarily involves Pessary treatment and surgical corrections, but complications, recurrence and postoperative complications remain common.^[7] Therefore, safe, conservative, and Ayurvedic modalities for prevention from further disease progression and management is both relevant and necessary.

Each vaginal birth stretches and sometimes tears the pelvic floor muscles, fascia and connective tissue. Higher parity especially multiple vaginal deliveries is a primary risk factor for Pelvic Organ Prolapse. Pregnancy hormones like relaxin and progesterone increase connective tissue laxity, making the pelvic floor more susceptible to damage. First vaginal

birth causes the largest single increase in risk, but subsequent births add incremental damage. Prevalence of Pelvic Organ Prolapse increases from 40 years of age, perimenopausal age due to laxity of perineal supportive structures, estrogen deficiency & reduction in collagen. Estrogen deficiency leads to atrophy of the urogenital tract, thinning of the vaginal mucosa, reduction in collagen and elastin content, and overall decline in pelvic floor muscle tone. Physical workload at home like heavy lifting, prolonged standing and squatting for long hours for cooking, cleaning can weaken pelvic floor support over time.

The *Nidana* of *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse) in the current case seems to be multiparity i.e., 4 full term normal vaginal deliveries, strenuous household activities like weight lifting and excessive bending which is combined with the age factor, the patient being 42 years old, which represents the patient is in climacteric period, during which pelvic organs undergo atrophic changes, estrogen levels start to decline and perimenopausal symptoms begin. All these factors are responsible for *Vata Dosha Prakopa* leading to *Mamsa, Meda, Asthi* and *Snayu Dushti* finally getting *Sthana Samsraya* at *Yoni* leading to weakness of supporting structures of *Yoni*. This causes *Vimargagamana* of pelvic organs from their *Swasthana* producing *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse). Here the patient presented with the symptoms like feeling of mass in the vagina, increased frequency of micturition and low back pain, which are typical symptoms observed in Pelvic Organ Prolapse.

The reference of *Lodhra-Katutumbi* can be found in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Stirogadhikara*, 141th verse and “*Yonidardhyakara*” effect has been mentioned.

लोधतुम्बीफलालेपो योनिदार्ढ्यं करोति च ।

- भैषज्य रत्नावली/स्त्रीरोगाधिकार /१४१

Table no. 3: *Rasapanchaka* of *Dravyas* in *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila*.

	<i>LODHRA</i> ^[8]	<i>KATUTUMBI</i> ^[9]	<i>TILA TAILA</i> ^[10]
BOTANICAL NAME	<i>Symplocos racemose Roxb.</i>	<i>Lagenaria vulgaris Ser.</i>	<i>Sesamum indicum Linn.</i>
PART USED	<i>Twak</i>	<i>Apakwa Phala</i>	-
RASA	<i>Kashaya</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Tikta (Kashaya Anurasa)</i>
GUNA	<i>Grahi</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Guru, Sookshma, Vishada, Vyavayi</i>
VEERYA	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Ushna</i>
VIPAKA	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Madhura</i>
DOSHA KARMA	<i>Shleshmaghna</i>	<i>Vatapittanashaka</i>	<i>Vatahara</i>
ROGAGHNA KARMA	<i>Raktastambhaka, Vranaropaka,</i>	<i>Vranahara, Shoolahara,</i>	<i>Balya, Brimhana, Garbhashayashodhana,</i>

	<i>Shothaghna, Balya</i>	<i>Shophahara</i>	<i>Yonishoolahara, Sthairyakara</i>
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DISCUSSION ON PROBABLE MODE OF ACTION OF *LODHRA-KATUTUMBI TAILA*

Shoshana action of *Kashaya Rasa* present in the drugs may help in reduction of feeling of mass per vagina.^[11] *Grahi* and *Sthambhana* properties of drugs may oppose *Chala Guna* and helps to hold organs in position and thereby reduces the traction effect.^[11] Flavonoids, tannin, saponins present in the drugs may help in strengthening the pelvic floor as it prevents tissue damage due to its antioxidant action. These components help to strengthen the connective tissues supporting the uterus and reduces low back ache.^[11] It is mentioned that *Lodhra* does *Sankocha* of *Shleshmala Twacha* and provides strength.^[12] *Kashaya Rasa* (astringent property), *Shoshana*, *Stambhana* and *Grahi* actions which helps to constrict the cells and brings compactness in the tissues. *Lodhra* contains phytoestrogens and studies show presence of estrogen receptors in the vaginal mucosa and uterosacral ligaments, hence effective in pelvic organ prolapse due to estrogen deficiency.^[13] Moreover, *Tila Taila* is *Vatahara*, *Madhura Vipaka*, *Balya*, *Brimhana*, *Sthairyakara*, hence when used as *Yonipichu*, it carries these properties along with the properties of particular drugs and provides strength to the vaginal tissues and supporting structures.

CONCLUSION

The present case highlights the promising role of *Lodhra-Katutumbi Taila Yonipichudharana* as a safe, effective, and non-surgical intervention for Pelvic Organ Prolapse. Alongside lifestyle modifications, this therapy not only provided significant symptomatic relief but also demonstrated measurable anatomical improvement. Its holistic approach strengthens pelvic support structures, and enhances quality of life without adverse effects. This case emphasizes the potential of Ayurvedic local therapies like *Yonipichudharana*, as viable alternatives to conventional management in *Yonibhramsha* (Pelvic Organ Prolapse).

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